

Voltage Stability of Microgrid with Grid-Connected Wind Farm

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Abstract. In this paper, we present a robust algorithm for tuning the parameters of a PID controller for automatic voltage regulator (AVR) of synchronous generator (SG). Our motivation for this work originates from the increased penetration of intermittent renewable energy sources (RES), which can cause voltage disturbances in the grid to which they are connected. Our goal is to develop a regulator that can mitigate disturbances in the grid resulting from renewable sources fluctuations while also remaining robust to errors in system modeling. The objective is to minimize the integral absolute error index (IAE) while taking into account predetermined values for M_s and M_p . M_s represents the maximum sensitivity function modulus, which is the transfer function of the coupled system from the output disturbance to the output. M_p represents the maximum complementary sensitivity function modulus, which is the closed-loop transfer function from the reference to the output. This guarantees sufficient reserves of stability for the entire system while also facilitating effective response to reference changes, as will be demonstrated and explained in the paper. The problem is analyzed and its solution is implemented using Matlab Simulink model.

Keywords: AVR, PID Controller, Grid-Connected Sources, RES, Robustness.

1 Introduction

The AVR provides regulation of the terminal voltage of the SG. Besides that, power system stability issues are affected by excitation system and the AVR [1]. Transient stability is to be enhanced in the presence of system variations: load changes, power line failures, short circuits, power plant outages. A robust and fast-response AVR can improve large-signal transient stability by increasing the ability of the power system to maintain synchronism when subjected to a severe transient disturbance and operating point variations. However, the fast-response AVR action can reduce damping of the electromechanical oscillations, thus, in that way it deteriorates oscillation stability.

Proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers are widely used in industry in order to regulate various process variables [2]. Such practice is also present in AVR where the PID controller is used to regulate voltage at SG terminals [3]. In situations

where feasible, the proportional-integral (PI) controller is used as well, instead of the PID controller, because of its simple structure and simple tuning rules [4]. The derivative term in PID and second order derivative term in PID2 structure still causes significant difficulties in its tuning and implementation [5], [6], mainly because of the presence of high-frequency measurement noise.

The algorithm provided in this paper is applicable for tuning both PI and PID controllers. However, considering the greater complexity associated with tuning a PID controller, the presentation will focus on the outcome related to the PID regulator.

RES have emerged as critical components of global efforts to achieve sustainable energy systems, mitigate climate change and ensure energy security [7]. However, the inherent discontinuity of sources like solar and wind has given rise to concerns over grid stability. Fluctuations in power generation can lead to frequency deviations, voltage instability, and increased system imbalances. This paper will discuss the integration of RES and their impact on the grid.

2 Controller design

2.1 Plant model

The plant model consists of serial connections of the amplifier (A), exciter (E) and generator (G), and when the outputs of the amplifier and exciter are not saturated the following plant model can be derived:

$$G_p(s) = \frac{K_a K_e K_g}{(T_a s + 1)(T_e s + 1)(T_g s + 1)} \quad (1)$$

where K_a , K_e , K_g are gains of the amplifier, exciter and generator, respectively, and T_a , T_e , T_g are time constants of the amplifier, exciter and generator, respectively.

In the current context, it is reasonable to neglect the amplifier's gain and time constant ($K_a=1$, $T_a=0$), so the plant model is:

$$G_p(s) = \frac{K_e K_g}{(T_e s + 1)(T_g s + 1)} \quad (2)$$

2.2 The optimized PID controller

The PID controller has four parameters and has the following structure:

$$C(s) = \frac{K_i + sK_p + s^2 K_d}{s} G_f(s), G_f = \frac{1}{T_f s + 1} \quad (3)$$

where T_f is time constant of noise filter.

In Fig. 1 it is shown the two degree of freedom PID controller for SG with exciter. The signal $d(t)$ represents disturbance input, the signal $n(t)$ represents measurement

noise input, while reference input, system output and control signal are marked with $r(t)$, $y(t)$ and $u(t)$, respectively.

Bearing in mind definitions of the maximum sensitivities:

$$M_s = \max_{\omega} |S(j\omega)| = \max_{\omega} \left| \frac{1}{1 + C(j\omega)G_p(j\omega)} \right| \quad (4)$$

$$M_p = \max_{\omega} |T(j\omega)| = \max_{\omega} \left| \frac{C(j\omega)G_p(j\omega)}{1 + C(j\omega)G_p(j\omega)} \right| \quad (5)$$

$$M_n = \max_{\omega} \left| \frac{C(j\omega)}{1 + C(j\omega)G_p(j\omega)} \right| \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1. The two degree of freedom PID controller for SG with exciter.

The constrained optimization problem is defined with:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{K_p, K_i, K_d} J & \quad (7) \\ M_s(K_p, K_i, K_d) &= M_s^* \\ M_p(K_p, K_i, K_d) &= M_p^* \end{aligned}$$

The constrained optimization problem is defined with:

$$J = IAE = \int_0^{\infty} |e_d(t)| dt, e_d(t) = d(t) = h(t), h(t) - \text{Heaviside step function} \quad (8)$$

To sum up main points: The novel tuning method for PID AVR controller is proposed to meet the following specification:

- Optimize load disturbance response (make IAE small)
- Maximum of sensitivity function modulus M_s is equal to M_s^*
- Maximum of complementary sensitivity function modulus M_p is equal to M_p^*
- By adjusting the value of T_f , we can attain the desired value of M_n

2.3 The relation between M_s , M_p and model's robustness

Bode diagram graphically illustrates the frequency response characteristics of a system and it is shown in the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Bode diagram.

Bode diagram consists of two components: a Bode magnitude plot, which represents the magnitude of the frequency response and a Bode phase plot, which represents the phase shift at various frequencies. Two variables provide insights into the robustness and stability of a control system – Phase margin (Φ_{pf}) and Gain margin (d).

Phase margin measures how much additional phase shift can be introduced in the system before it becomes unstable. It indicates the system's ability to tolerate phase delays without leading to instability.

$$\Phi_{pf} = 180^\circ + \arg W(j\omega_1) \quad (9)$$

$$\Phi_{pf} > 0 \text{ for stable closed-loop system}$$

A higher phase margin is generally desirable as it indicates greater stability reserves ($\Phi_{pf} > 30^\circ$).

Gain margin represents the amount by which the system's gain can be increased before instability occurs. It quantifies the system's robustness against changes in gain.

$$d = \frac{1}{|W(j\omega_g)|} \quad (10)$$

$$d > 1 \text{ for stable closed-loop system}$$

Similar to phase margin, a larger gain margin implies more stability.

The relation between M_s , M_p , Φ_{pf} and d is as follows [8]:

$$d \geq \frac{M_s}{M_s - 1}, \Phi_{pf} \geq 2\arcsin\left(\frac{1}{2M_s}\right) \quad (11)$$

$$d \geq 1 + \frac{1}{M_p}, \Phi_{pf} \geq 2\arcsin\left(\frac{1}{2M_p}\right) \quad (12)$$

3 Simulation Tests

3.1 Finding parameters of the PID controller

A SG is connected to the grid using an transformer (15.75 kV/25 kV) leading to the location of the Wind Farm. The Wind Farm comprises of 40 turbines, each with an apparent power of 1.75 MVA, that are connected via an transformer (575 V/25 kV) through a 30 km transmission line to the rest of the power grid. Our hybrid-system is linked to the 120 kV grid using an transformer (25 kV/120 kV). The Fig.3 shows the entire system used in this paper.

Fig. 3. Model of the entire system.

The main parameters of the SG used in this paper are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Main parameters of the SG.

Symbol	Description	Value
S_n	Rated Apparent power	297 MVA
V_n	Rated stator voltage	15.75 kV
I_n	Rated stator current	9.27 kA
pf	Rated power factor	0.85
f_n	Rated frequency	50 Hz
V_f	Rated field voltage	424 V
I_f	Rated field current	1930 A
X_d	Direct axis synchronous reactance	1.932 pu
X_d'	Direct axis transient reactance	0.312 pu
X_d''	Direct axis sub-transient reactance	0.21 pu
X_q	Quadrature axis synchronous machine	1.8 pu
R_s	Stator Resistance	0.004 pu
T_d'	Direct axis short circuit transient time constant	1.25 s
T_d''	Direct axis short circuit sub-transient time constant	0.05 s

SG can be approximated using a first-order linear function with parameters $K_g=1$ and $T_g=8s$. Other parameters of the system are: $K_e=1$, $T_e=1.6s$ and the predefined parameter of regulator is $T_f=0.08s$.

Target values for M_p and M_s are 1.5 and 1.6, respectively, corresponding to gain margin and phase margin values of $d=3$ and $\Phi_{pf}=38.7^\circ$.

The parameters for PID controller were obtained by using the MATLAB function `fmincon` to solve our constrained optimization problem (7):

$$K_p = 15.3890, K_i = 2.8678, K_d = 4.4007 \text{ while } IAE=0.3475$$

Value of the M_n (sensitivity to measurement noise) is $M_n = 55$.

The algorithm offers the flexibility to adjust the value of M_n . If the acquired value is high, it can be fine-tuned by modifying T_f , as there exists a relationship between M_n and T_f given by:

$$M_n = \frac{K_d}{T_f} \quad (13)$$

3.2 Behavior of the controller

The sequence utilized consists of the following steps:

- 1) Introducing a negative grid disturbance of 10% at 60s.
- 2) Introducing a positive grid disturbance of 10% at 90s
- 3) Applying a negative step reference change of 5% to SG terminal voltage U_g at 120s.
- 4) Applying a positive step reference change of 5% to U_g at 150s.
- 5) Implementing a negative step reference change of 30% to SG active power P at 180s.
- 6) Activating the Wind Farm with a wind speed of 15 m/s at 200s.
- 7) Deactivating the Wind Farm at 240s.

The conclusive outcomes are illustrated in the following figures, Fig.4 - Fig.13:

Fig. 4. Terminal voltage of the synchronous generator - U_g .

Fig. 5. Control signal - U_f .

Fig. 6. Active power of the synchronous generator - P .

Fig. 7. Reactive power of the synchronous generator – Q .

Fig.4. illustrates the system's response with the PID controller whose parameters were determined using the algorithm presented in this paper. The performance of the controller show adequate speed response and absence of overshoot. Furthermore, the area beneath the load disturbance response curve is notably reduced. Fig. 5 shows the control signal, which is excitation voltage U_f . Fig. 6 illustrates the active power P of the SG, and the occurrence of undamped oscillations is normal. Fig. 7 shows the reactive power of the SG. Figures 8 and 9 show that whether or not the SG is connected to the grid, the response of active power and reactive power in the wind farm behaves similarly (the performance of the wind park is unaffected by the addition of a SG to the grid).

Fig. 8. Active power of the Wind Farm.

Fig. 9. Reactive power of the Wind Farm.

However there is an improvement in the grid voltage response on both the 25 kV and 120 kV sides:

Fig. 10. Grid voltage on the 25 kV side.

Fig. 11. Grid voltage on the 120 kV side.

Figures 10 and 11 show the grid voltage response on the 25 kV and 120 kV side, respectively. They present the moment when the grid voltage disturbance is introduced at the 120 kV side of the grid and it is evident that when a SG is connected to the grid, the voltage fluctuates less.

Figures 12 and 13 show the grid voltage response on the 25 kV and 120 kV side, respectively, at the moment when the wind farm is activated and it is notable too, that voltage fluctuates less when SG is connected to the grid.

Fig. 12. Grid voltage on the 25 kV side.

Fig. 13. Grid voltage on the 120 kV side.

4 Conclusion

In this paper is presented robust algorithm for fine-tuning a PID controller's parameters, with the primary objective of minimizing the IAE. The result is a stable closed-loop controller with significant stability margin. The method for limiting the maximum gain between measuring device and the control signal is suggested, which help to reduce the amount of noise that enters the system. Furthermore, the introduction of a SG into the system alongside the wind park leads to an improvement in the grid voltage stability.

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